

LEUPROLIDE ACETATE VERSUS GOSERELIN ACETATE: A RESEARCH STUDY TO ASSESS THE HORMONAL THERAPY EFFECTS ON RELIEF OF LOWER UTI SYMPTOMS, VOLUME REDUCTION AND PROSTATE CANCER

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Abstract:

Background: Lower urinary tract symptoms complaints of the prostate carcinoma (Pca) patients have an association with parallel ageing bladder and benign prostate hyperplasia.

Objective: The objective of this research was to highlight and compare the effect of leuprolide acetate with Goserelin acetate on TPV (Total Prostate Volume), PVR (Post Voiding Residue), and Qmax (Maximum Flow Rate Reduction and IPSS (International Prostate Symptom Score) among advanced Pca patients

Materials and Methods: This research was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from April 2017 to July 2018 on a total of seventy-one patients with Pca. After analysis fifty-one, suitable patients were short-listed and divided into two groups Group A & B respectively treated with Goserelin acetate (10.8 mg) for three months and leuprolide acetate (22.5 mg) for three months. Gleason score, Age, T-stage, pre-treatment and post-treatment PSA (Prostate Specific Antigen), level of testosterone, IPSS, TPV, Qmax and PVR values were documented retrospectively. We also assessed the change in the parameters at an interval of three months.

Results: The research included fifty-one patients for assessment process. There was no statistical difference among patients for mean decrease in the percentage of PSA for both groups (Group – A 98.7% and Group – B 98.4%; P-Value = 0.9) and testosterone (Group – A 92.9 % and Group – B 96.4 %; P-Value = 0.15) from baseline to a period of six months; whereas, TPV decreased by $(-20.2\% \pm 4.8)$ and $(-15.6\% \pm 1.04)$, the median decrease in the IPSS was $(-34.77\% \pm 8.8)$ and $(-19.77\% \pm 6.1)$, the median increase in Qmax was $(45.34\% \pm 10.16)$ and $(23.21\% \pm 6.93)$ and median decrease in PVR was $(-31.54\% \pm 8.4)$ and $(-19.23\% \pm 5.5)$ for Group – A & B (P-Value < 0.05).

Conclusion: The outcomes reflect an improvement in the Goserelin acetate parameters than Leuprolide acetate. The Goserelin acetate superiority based on reduced TPV, IPSS and PVR. Though the time for PSA follow-up was short; but there was no significant difference in the initial oncological findings.

Keywords: Prostate Carcinoma (Pca), TPV (Total Prostate Volume), PVR (Post Voiding Residue), Qmax (Maximum Flow Rate), IPSS (International Prostate Symptom Score), Goserelin Acetate and Leuprolide Acetate.

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INTRODUCTION:

Prostate carcinoma is a common malignant cancer with higher male mortality rate due to malignancy [1]. Back in 2004, the occurrence was 35/ 100,000 due to prostate cancer [2]. Survival and improvement are possible through ADT (Androgen Deprivation Therapy) for the advanced and metastatic stage of the Pca [3]. The hormone which releases Gonadotropin (GnRH) agonists is commonly used ADT. Peripheral zone originates seventy percent of Pca which is mostly asymptomatic until prostatic urethra compressing size growth, metastasis or bladder neck [4]. Therefore, lower urinary tract symptoms complaints of the prostate carcinoma (Pca) patients have an association with parallel ageing bladder and benign prostate hyperplasia [5]. TPV, IPSS, PVR and Qmax are important for the treatment and planning of such patients. It has been established in the literature that ADT can potently reduce TPV from thirty percent to fifty-five percent [6, 7]. Hormonal therapy is effective to reduce tumour volume and TPV; the downsizing of prostate gland effects the values of Qmax, IPSS and PVR [8]. The effect of GnRH agonists on LUTS have not been well established in any of the research studies. In order to address the lapse and loopholes we have carried out this research with an objective to highlight and compare the effect of leuprolide acetate with Goserelin acetate on TPV (Total Prostate Volume), PVR (Post Voiding Residue), Qmax (Maximum Flow Rate Reduction and IPSS (International Prostate Symptom Score) among advanced Pca patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was carried out at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from April 2017 to July 2018 on a total of seventy-one patients with Pca. After analysis fifty-one, suitable patients were short-listed and divided into two groups Group A & B respectively treated with Goserelin acetate (10.8 mg) for three months and leuprolide acetate (22.5 mg) for three months. Gleason score, Age, T-stage, pre-treatment and post-treatment PSA (Prostate Specific Antigen), level of testosterone, IPSS, TPV, Qmax and PVR values were documented retrospectively. We also assessed the change in the

parameters at an interval of three months. We did not include all those patients who presented indwelling urinary catheter, alpha-adrenoceptor blocker treatment and alpha reductase inhibitors treatment, evident nervous system disorder, received pelvic surgery or underwent urinary tract surgery. All study protocols were implemented on the shortlisted fifty-one patients. All bicalutamide patients were treated for an initial ten days with once daily dose of (50 mg) or flare protection and on last day we inserted GnRH agents subcutaneously into the abdominal wall.

Blood samples were collected for the analysis of levels of PSA and testosterone with validated chemiluminescence approach an initial stage of ADT. Same analysis was repeated after three and six months. Urologist also performed uroflowmetry and ultrasonography after every three months for drug administration. Every patient completed the IPSS questionnaire for the assessment of LUTS [9]. It includes seven UTI symptoms including frequency, incomplete emptying, urgency, intermittency, straining, weak stream and nocturia [8]. LUTS was divided into the categories of Mild with a range of IPSS as (1 – 7), moderate (8 – 19) and severe (20 – 35) [10]. Data were analyzed through SPSS software (P-Value < 0.05).

RESULTS:

The research included fifty-one patients for assessment process. There was no statistical difference among patients for mean decrease in the percentage of PSA for both groups (Group – A 98.7% and Group – B 98.4%; P-Value = 0.9) and testosterone (Group – A 92.9 % and Group – B 96.4 %; P-Value = 0.15) from baseline to a period of six months; whereas, TPV decreased by (-20.2% ± 4.8) and (-15.6% ± 1.04), the median decrease in the IPSS was (-34.77% ± 8.8) and (-19.77% ± 6.1), the median increase in Qmax was (45.34% ± 10.16) and (23.21% ± 6.93) and median decrease in PVR was (-31.54% ± 8.4) and (-19.23% ± 5.5) for Group – A & B (P-Value < 0.05).

Detailed Baseline/demographic features are given in Table – I and detailed change of parameters from baseline to six months are given in Table – II.

Table – I: Baseline Characteristics

Baseline Characteristics	Goserelin acetate (10.8 mg) (24)	Leuprolide acetate (22.5 mg) (27)	P-Value
Age (Years)	67.4 (48 – 80)	64.25 (46 – 83)	0.035
Time from Initial Treatment	61	57	
T - I	8	11	
T - II	12	10	

T - III/IV	4	6	
Gleason score ≤ 7	7	9	
Gleason score ≥ 8	17	18	
TPV (mL) day of 0	64.12 (28-136)	81.18 (24-110)	0.06
IPSS day of 0	13.45 (4-29)	12.39 (6-26)	0.06
Qmax day of 0	12.4 (5-23)	12.19 (4-21)	0.11
PVR day of 0	73.02 (29-156)	75.9 (20-98)	0.27
PSA levels, ng/mL (mean)	25.6 (4-100)	30.45 (4-81)	0.09
Testosterone, ng/mL (mean)	2.77 (1.1-6.6)	2.98 (1.53-6.2)	0.11

Table – II: Change of Parameters from Baseline to Six Months

Initial to 6 Months	Goserelin Acetate		Leuprolide Acetate		P-Value
	Percentage	± Tolerance	Percentage	± Tolerance	
PSA	-98.70	0.90	-98.4	0.40	0.9
TT	-92.90	5.80	-96.4	6.90	0.15
TPV	-20.20	4.80	-15.6	1.04	0.02
IPSS	-34.77	8.80	-19.77	6.10	0.001
Qmax	45.34	10.16	23.21	6.93	0.001
PVR	-31.54	8.40	-19.23	5.50	0.01

DISCUSSION:

Hormone therapy can effectively treat metastatic and advanced Pca especially for those patients who are unable to manage radical treatment alternatives. GnRH receptor agonists help to obtain required levels of treatment for 90% of affected patients with serum testosterone (< 0.5 ng/mL) [11]. T serum levels may face a rapid increase in the first treatment episode. Therefore, patients receiving antiandrogen treatment for a period of ten days before the administration of the first injection may prevent clinical signs such as spinal cord compression, flare phenomenon, urethral obstruction and bone pain [1].

The major concern among Pca patients are the symptoms of the low urinary tract. Although, outcomes of certain studies indicate endocrine treatments efficacy for complaints about LUTS. No evidence is available about the effectiveness of Leuprolide acetate and Goserelin acetate on the improvement of Qmzx, PVR, TPV and IPSS [8, 12, 13]. The outcomes of this research reflect that there are positive effects of hormonal therapy on the symptoms of LUTS and prostate volume in the period of six months. Pca coexists with BPH that can result in LUTS. According to Lehrer, Pca patients presented mild, moderate and severe LUTS symptoms with the respective proportion of 55.6%, 37.1% and 7.3% [14]. Outcomes of our research show better outcomes in the parameters of ADT during the first month. Other studies report decreases in the TPV value from 27% to 48% in the outcomes of ADT [15, 16]. In this research, the decrease in the TPV which is secondary to the hormone therapy in Goserelin group was 20.2% and for Leuprolide group 15.6% in the period of six months which is in agreement with the past studies.

Various studies have also determined the testosterone suppression effects on bladder outlet obstruction. GnRH blockage in epithelial cells and prostate smooth muscle allows pro-inflammatory cytokines down-regulation, α1-adrenoreceptors and growth factors which are involved in these cells. The decrease in TPV and improvement in LUTS were accepted in smooth muscle relaxation patients [10, 17]. This research reported significant improvement in IPS scores for Goserelin acetate was respectively (-34.77% ± 8.8) versus (-19.77% ± 6.1) in both groups. There is a relation between voiding scores and Qmzx and PVR associated IPSS values [13]. The outcomes show that improvement in the maximum flow rate (45.34% ± 10.16) and reduced postvoid residual volume (-31.54% ± 8.4) were reduced in Leuprolide acetate than Goserelin acetate (P < 0.01). For the comparison of GnRH agonists, some of the authors show no difference between Leuprolide acetate and Goserelin acetate [3]. Goserelin groups presented superiority over Leuprolide groups [18].

CONCLUSION:

The major objective of hormonal therapy was to manage patients with metastatic and advanced prostate carcinoma for such patients unable to afford radical management alternatives, ADT effect was observed on prostate volume and voiding symptoms. The improvement in the Goserelin acetate voiding parameters was determined better in comparison with Leuprolide acetate. Goserelin acetate can better control the reduction of IPSS, PVR and TPV.

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